

A Systematic Review Protocol: Scoping Review of Secondary Education Students' Comprehension of Climate Change

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Introduction

Since the publication of the systematic review "Characterization of Educational Research on Climate Change among Secondary Students" (García-Vinuesa & Meira-Cartea, 2019)—which identified 84 studies on the comprehension of climate change among middle and high school students from 1993 to October 2017 by exploring Web of Science, Scopus, Scielo, Redalyc, and Dialnet databases—no subsequent review has thoroughly explored this scope of knowledge, despite the increasing interest in climate change education in recent years.

The present study assumes that no reviews have been conducted to update the results of the previous review. This assumption is based on the results of an exploratory search in which only one relevant study emerged: the review by Nepraš et al. (2022). They performed a literature review on climate change education and identified 43 studies between 2001 and 2020 in the Web of Science database. However, this review focused on mixed populations, considering only primary and lower secondary education students and teachers, and not all secondary education levels.

Therefore, the current scoping review aims to build on the work of García-Vinuesa and Meira-Cartea (2019) and Nepraš et al. (2022) by examining middle and high school students' understanding of climate change across all levels of secondary education.

This protocol was drafted using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis Protocols Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) (Tricco et al., 2018). As previously mentioned, the aim of this protocol is to plan the execution of a scoping systematic review on the comprehension of climate change among secondary education students. This scoping review is an update of a previous systematic review (García-Vinuesa & Meira-Cartea, 2019) conducted by one of the present authors.

Review questions

The central research question guiding this scoping review is: "What existing literature is available on the understanding of climate change among secondary education students between 2017 and 2023?"

The following subquestions have also been identified:

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1. What are the publishing trends regarding climate change and secondary education students in the past six years?
2. How has climate change education research related to secondary education students evolved since 2017?

Methods

Systematic scoping reviews serve as comprehensive evidence synthesis endeavors that systematically explore the landscape of a specific academic domain (Gutierrez-Bucheli et al., 2022). They pursue diverse objectives, including assessing the breadth, diversity, and characteristics of available evidence on the topic under scrutiny, evaluating the feasibility of deeper exploration, synthesizing identified methods and findings within the field, updating and complementing prior reviews, and identifying novel research avenues (Tricco et al., 2018). The aim of this scoping review is to update a previous one (García-Vinuesa & Meira-Cartea, 2019).

Presently, numerous standardized protocols offer guidance for report preparation during systematic review conduct: PRISMA, SALSA, PRIOR, among others. These protocols are tailored to match the goals and peculiarities of each discipline and individual study. Primarily, they seek to ensure methodological quality and validity in review endeavors (Tricco et al., 2018). A notable adaptation of the PRISMA statement is the PRISMA-ScR, specifically crafted for systematic scoping reviews (Tricco et al., 2018). While these recommendations primarily originate from the health domain, Codina (2020) acknowledge their potential applicability in evidence synthesis within educational research. Notably, Gutierrez-Bucheli et al. (2022) emphasize their utility in environmental and sustainability education research.

Eligibility criteria

This study will utilize the Participant/Population, Concept, Context (PCC) framework, as recommended by Gutierrez-Bucheli et al. (2022), to align the research objectives with the selection of studies and to inform the design of eligibility criteria.

Participants/Population

This review will consider studies involving any student population.

Concept

This scoping review will encompass studies exploring cognitive aspects of climate change comprehension, including knowledge, perceptions, emotions, attitudes, willingness, etc.

Context

This review will focus on studies conducted within the context of middle and high school education (International Standard Classification of Education levels 2 and 3).

Types of sources

For this scoping review, we will assess published, peer-reviewed studies utilizing quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods design for inclusion. Excluded from consideration will be systematic reviews, grey literature, books and book chapters, conference papers and proceedings, as well as theses and dissertations. Studies from all countries will be eligible, but only documents written in English, Spanish, or Portuguese will be included. The publication timeframe for inclusion will span from 2017 to 2023.

Search strategy

The document search will be conducted in the Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) databases, renowned for their rigor, breadth, and the significant scientific scope of their indexed collections (Codina, 2020). Access will be performed from the University of Santiago de Compostela network, under the subscription of the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT).

As previously mentioned, the Participant/Population, Concept, Context (PCC) framework (Gutierrez-Bucheli et al., 2022) was followed to establish a search strategy that aligns with the objectives of this scoping review. Therefore, the search will be conducted in the search engines of WOS and Scopus in the fields of title, abstract, and keywords, focusing on the following terms: student, climate change, global warming, secondary, middle school, and high school. Thus, the search string to be used is as follows: (TITLE-ABS-KEY (student*) AND TITLE- ABS-KEY ("climate change" OR "global warming") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("secondary" OR "middle school" OR "high school")).

The reference list from the study by Nepraš et al. (2022) will be reviewed to confirm our findings, and we will also consult colleagues in climate change education research to identify any potentially overlooked studies

Study selection

The CADIMA online tool for conducting systematic reviews will be employed to support the process. It is a freely accessible online platform designed to assist in creating methodological reports for evidence synthesis. Distinguished from other open-source software programs, CADIMA offers users an easily navigable interface and a diverse array of services that are regularly updated (Kohl et al., 2018). It facilitates every step of the review process, including duplicate removal, independent and parallel reviewing, performing inter-reviewer consistency checks, and supporting the organization and extraction of data. In cases where papers do not meet the inclusion criteria, justifications will be documented in CADIMA to be included in the scoping review report.

An inter-reviewer consistency check will be conducted to achieve an acceptable Kappa index for eligibility criteria. Following that, two selection stages will be carried out:

1. Parallel reviewing to apply the PCC criteria through the examination of the title and abstract.
2. In-depth reading of the documents that pass the first stage.

The comprehensive findings will be described in the scoping review and depicted in a flow diagram.

Data extraction

CADIMA will assist in documenting all extracted data. In order to address the research questions, the extracted data will include the following bibliometric details: title, authors, affiliation, year of publication, publisher, keywords, type of study, techniques and instruments for recording participant information, sample sizes, educational level of the students, and country of origin of the students. This data will provide an overview of climate change education research concerning secondary education students' comprehension of climate change.

Data analysis and preparation

The data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics, which will be presented in maps, tables, and figures with the aim of providing a clear depiction of the evolution of climate change education.

Ethics and dissemination

Given that this scoping review doesn't involve participants and utilizes publicly available literature, ethical approval isn't required. Significant findings will be submitted to suitable peer-reviewed journals as a scoping review. Additionally, these findings might be shared at pertinent education conferences.

References

- Codina, L. (2020). How to do traditional or systematic bibliographic reviews using academic databases. *Revista Orl*, *11*(2), 139-153. <https://doi.org/10.14201/orl.22977>
- García-Vinuesa, A., & Meira Cartea, P. Á. (2019). Characterization of Educational Research on Climate Change among Secondary Students. *Revista mexicana de investigación educativa*, *24*(81), 507-535. <https://www.scielo.org.mx/pdf/rmie/v24n81/1405-6666-rmie-24-81-507.pdf>
- Gutierrez-Bucheli, L., Reid, A., & Kidman, G. (2022). Scoping reviews: Their development and application in environmental and sustainability education research. *Environmental Education Research*, *28*(5), 645-673. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2022.2047896>
- Kohl, C., McIntosh, E. J., Unger, S., Haddaway, N. R., Kecke, S., Schiemann, J., & Wilhelm, R. (2018). Online tools supporting the conduct and reporting of systematic reviews and systematic maps: a case study on CADIMA and review of existing tools. *Environmental Evidence*, *7*, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-018-0115-5>

Nepraš, K., Strejčková, T., & Kroufek, R. (2022). Climate Change Education in Primary and Lower Secondary Education: Systematic Review Results. *Sustainability*, 14(22), 14913. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142214913>

Tricco, A. C., Lillie, E., Zarin, W., O'Brien, K. K., Colquhoun, H., Levac, D., Moher, D., Peters, M., Horsley, T., Weeks, L., Hempel, S., Akl, E., Chang, C., McGowan, J., Stewart, L., Hartling, L., Aldcroft, A., Wilson, M., Garritty, C., Lewin, S., ... & Straus, S. E. (2018). PRISMA extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR): checklist and explanation. *Annals of internal medicine*, 169(7), 467-473. <https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-0850>